

Applying the Three Horizons approach in local and regional scenarios to support policy coherence in SDG implementation: Insights from arid Spain

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ABSTRACT

The Three Horizons for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is a novel participatory approach to co-create future sustainable scenarios for supporting the implementation of the United Nations 2030 Agenda. Whereas the approach has been applied to inform the design of global-scale sustainability scenarios based on regional perspectives, it has not been implemented to explore how local and regional scenarios can be connected across sites and scales to inform governance processes in the implementation of the SDGs. This study applies an adapted version of the Three Horizons for the SDGs approach in four sites at regional and local scales in Spanish drylands to explore its potential to support policy coherence at multiple governance scales for advancing SDG implementation through dialogue between actors from multiple sectors. We conducted four two-day in-person workshops with diverse actors ($n = 59$) to explore their perceptions about the desired futures, current concerns, and strategies to achieve sustainable futures in the region. Results reveal 27 similar and nine dissimilar themes related to desired futures and current concerns, respectively. These findings provide common ground and highlight different contextual realities between sites that may serve as a basis for harmonizing policy priorities for advancing regional and local SDG implementation. The study also identifies 19 themes encompassing multiple strategies with the potential to establish associations across sites and scales to coordinate actions in alignment with the 2030 Agenda. We argue that the adapted version of the Three Horizons for the SDGs approach can serve as a tool to support coherent multi-scale governance needed to achieve global sustainability goals. We discuss lessons learned and limitations encountered from using the approach that provides guidance for future experiences.

1. Introduction

The United Nations' 2030 Agenda, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), aims to guide global efforts to build a more sustainable world by 2030 (UN, 2015). It focuses on protecting human rights and the planet while fostering peace, partnerships, and justice (Jayasooria, 2016). The 2030 Agenda sets 17 SDGs and 169 targets to drive transformative change toward sustainable development, presenting challenges due to the complexity and interdependence behind the implementation of SDGs (UN, 2015). However, there are some pressing

discussions concerning the implementation of the SDGs (Malekpour et al., 2023). First, the SDGs implementation, as outlined in the 2030 Agenda, primarily focuses on a global scale, which can make it challenging to apply effectively at the local level (Jiménez-Aceituno et al., 2020; Biggeri, 2021). Second, the SDGs possess an indivisible nature, meaning they are interconnected and should be addressed in an integrated manner (Collste, 2021; Weitz et al. 2023). This can also be difficult to operationalize locally, where policies and actions are often developed through traditional "top-down" and sectoral approaches and focused on jurisdictional scales (Wyborn and Bixler, 2013; Biggeri,

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2021). These factors have led to the recognition that implementing the 2030 Agenda requires policy coherence through innovative approaches that foster coordination and alignment between the various scales of governance and their connection with the global SDGs while facilitating engagement between public, private, and social actors (Smoke and Nixon, 2016; Biggeri, 2021).

In recent years, the scientific community has provided a wide diversity of methodological approaches to assist the policy community in advancing toward implementing SDGs. These methodological approaches include participatory scenario planning approaches (e.g., Kanter et al., 2016; Collste et al., 2023), systemic and contextual interactions analysis (e.g., Nilsson et al., 2016; Weitz et al., 2018), modeling studies (e.g., Pedercini et al., 2019) and literature reviews (e.g., Allen et al., 2021). Despite efforts made in this matter throughout the global research and policy community, the United Nations official report, which provides a comprehensive midpoint assessment of the 2030 Agenda, highlights that countries have generally not been successful in implementing the SDGs, remaining many challenges in the different domains of their implementation (UN, 2023). Therefore, the report urges the world to redouble its efforts, emphasizing, among others, the research community's role in providing scientific inputs and tools to facilitate transformative change in society at different scales, accelerating new practices and initiatives to achieve sustainability.

The Three Horizons for the SDGs (3H4SDG) emerged recently as a novel participatory approach to co-create future scenarios that guide and support the execution and governance of the 2030 Agenda (Aguiar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023). It is an adaptation to the SDGs context of the Three Horizons (3H) framework proposed by Sharpe et al. (2016). The 3H framework was initially described in the literature as a management-oriented tool to build a range of plausible and coherent futures (Baghai et al., 1999). A few decades later, Sharpe et al. (2016) proposed an adaptation of the 3H framework to facilitate deliberations about uncertain futures, considering features from the present and envisioning strategies for sustainability. The 3H has been increasingly used in various contexts and topics. For example, within the Seeds of Good Anthropocene project (Bennett et al., 2016) it has been combined with scenario planning techniques to build positive future scenarios based on existing novel initiatives (or 'seeds') that have the potential—under the proper conditions—to catalyze systemic transformative change (Pereira et al., 2018, 2019; Falardeau et al., 2019; Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2020). The 3H has also been used to co-design pathways toward improved human–wildlife coexistence (Jiren et al., 2021) and biodiversity conservation (Schaal et al., 2023). Furthermore, the 3H has served to analyze multiple types of motivations and values to collectively pursue sustainable futures (Harmáčková et al., 2022). The adaptation of the 3H to the context of the 2030 Agenda, the 3H4SDG approach, was created to generate spaces for collective reflection about the aspirations that people hold for the future (aligned with the achievement of the SDGs), the unsustainable elements of the present system that they want to transform, and the strategies needed for transitioning from the present toward the desired futures (see Aguilar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023). It was initially applied in the African Dialogue on 'The World in 2050' and proved to be helpful in facilitating inclusive and plural discussions to develop bottom-up pathways toward the SDGs—emphasizing perspectives from the Global South—and guide the design of global-scale sustainability pathways based on regional perspectives of sustainability futures (Aguilar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023). Among the potentialities identified of the 3H4SDG approach, the authors highlight its potential to understand how regional and local pathways toward desired futures can be connected across areas and scales to inform multi-scale governance structures for advancing in SDG implementation in an integrated and coordinated manner (Aguilar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023). However, this potential attributed to the 3H4SDG approach has yet to be explored.

To contribute to filling this knowledge gap, an adapted version of the 3H4SDG approach that we named 3H-Causal Loop Diagrams (3H-CLD)

has been applied within the XPaths project (<https://www.xpathsfutures.org>) in case studies in dryland regions: Spain, Senegal, and Brazil. The 3H-CLD combines the 3H framework with innovative techniques such as system thinking tools and arts-based activities to engage multiple actors in visioning pathways to sustainable futures (Aguiar et al., under review). We focused on dryland regions because these areas occupy almost half of the Earth's surface. Their peculiar hydrological regime, which makes water its main limiting factor, and the increasing pressures derived from their more than 2 billion inhabitants make them one of the most vulnerable ecosystems on the planet (UNCCD, 2017). Therefore, drylands have significant social, economic, and ecological importance, and there is an urgent need to enable sustainable pathways to progress toward implementing SDGs. This article is centered on the Spanish case study, specifically in Spanish drylands (Southeast of Spain). This region has undergone significant environmental changes with large-scale economic, socio-cultural, and ecological impacts (Quintas-Soriano et al., 2016), and it is widely recognized that it needs to transition to a socio-economic model based on sustainability (Castro et al., 2019). Our working hypothesis is that the 3H-CLD can guide the identification of pathways that connect regional and local governance scales with the global 2030 Agenda for facilitating the coherent implementation of SDGs. According to this hypothesis, our research aims to examine the potential of the 3H-CLD approach to support policy coherence at multiple governance scales for advancing SDG implementation through dialogue between actors from multiple sectors. To test our hypothesis, we applied the 3H-CLD approach through four identical workshops in Spanish drylands at the regional and local scales to explore desired futures, current concerns and potential strategies to achieve sustainable futures in the region. Building on the elicited knowledge from the workshops, we identified themes concerning the desired futures and current concerns perceived by actors across scales that provided common ground while highlighting different contextual realities between sites to harmonize policy priorities for advancing SDG implementation. In addition, we determined themes related to the strategies to achieve the desired futures and explored potential associations among them as a basis to coordinate actions across sites and scales in alignment with the 2030 Agenda. On this basis, we argue that the 3H-CLD approach can support policy coherence for advancing SDG implementation. We finally discussed the potential contributions and limitations of the adopted approach.

2. Methods

In this section, we describe the ontological framing and epistemology of the research, the study area, and the methods used for data collection and analysis.

2.1. Ontological framing and epistemology

The literature widely recognizes that ontological and epistemological beliefs influence how research is understood and conducted, as well as outcomes and results (Darwin-Holmes, 2020). To frame our research, we adopted four core ontological positions based on the assumption that *SDG implementation* requires *policy coherence* from a *multi-scale governance* perspective through *approaches that enable transformative change* in existing systems.

SDG implementation. The United Nations adopted the 2030 Agenda as a global road map to achieve sustainable development (UN, 2015). Whereas the 2030 Agenda has evoked optimism due to the transformational intent underlying many SDGs and their strategic merit, given their international alignment, it has also been highly criticized for being inconsistent, difficult to implement, quantify, and monitor (Swain, 2018). Critiques also state, among others, that it ignores local nuance, encourages economic growth ideas, and reproduces a universal template grounded in a Western and neoliberal ideology (Arora-Jonsson, 2023). Despite its critics and limitations, in this research, we conceived the

2030 Agenda as the current global instrument that offers the practical chance to engage people in transformative processes toward global sustainability goals.

Policy coherence. Policy coherence is understood as the harmonization, coordination, and cooperation of mutually reinforcing policies through the achievement of synergies or the creation of positive interactions between policy objectives or actions (both horizontally and vertically) across scales and sectors within a given governance context (OECD, 2007; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016; Lieu et al., 2018; Evans et al., 2023). On this conceptual basis, we considered that policy coherence in a given context could be supported by identifying critical themes to 1) harmonize policy priorities and 2) coordinate actions across areas and scales.

Multi-scale governance. Sustainability issues require attention to the scale of governance (Wyborn and Bixler, 2013). System dynamics at larger spatial scales of governance can influence system function at lower scales, and, at the same time, those that operate at smaller scales can also aggregate change to generate influence at higher scales (Enfors-Kautsky et al., 2018). As sustainability issues are deeply interconnected, it is well-recognized that they need to be addressed in an integrative manner from local to global governance scales to produce coherent and optimal outcomes for sustainability (Lemos and Agrawal, 2006; Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021). On this basis, we assumed that understanding interconnections across governance scales is critical to support policy coherence in SDG implementation.

Transformative change and the 3H as an approach for facilitating it. It has become widely recognized that transformative change is needed to achieve a sustainable global future. Transformative change is defined as a fundamental, system-wide reorganization across technological, economic, and social factors, including paradigms, goals, and values, to enable current trends toward more sustainable ones (Díaz et al., 2019). Transformative change can be enabled, strengthened, and accelerated through innovative approaches to help state and non-state actors to work collectively by envisioning priority challenges and addressing interventions for acting in favor of sustainability from local to global scales (Díaz et al., 2019; Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021). Among the various approaches available in the past decades to support this social challenge, we focused on the 3H framework since its practice is conceived as a valuable way to support transformative pattern shifts (Sharpe et al., 2016; Fazey et al., 2020). Specifically, we centered on an adapted version of the 3H framework to the context of the 2030 Agenda (Aguilar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023), and we built from this approach through an interplay of three steps focused on identifying: Step 1) a desirable vision of the future (a system we want to transform to) (H3), Step 2) the undesirable features of the current system (a system we want to transform from) (H1), and Step 3) necessary changes to shift from the current undesirable features to the desirable vision (H2). We presumed that an adapted version of the 3H in the context of the 2030 Agenda (the 3H-CLD) could be helpful to identify themes that connect regional and local governance scales with the global 2030 Agenda for facilitating policy coherence for SDG implementation through dialogue between actors from multiple sectors.

Epistemologically, our research was inspired by second-order science, which is considered a way of doing science to produce more socially relevant research to enhance transformative change for sustainability (Fazey et al., 2018; Fazey et al., 2020). Second-order science focuses on creating change from within the system being studied (rather than outside) by opening the space to include different forms of knowledge that provide new opportunities to learn and reflect more directly on how the system can be transformed (Fazey et al., 2018). This way of doing science is consistent with the recent call in sustainability science, especially in the area of the 3H framework (e.g., Sharpe et al., 2016; Fazey et al., 2020).

We focused our research on collecting three forms of knowledge: 1) creative knowledge to envision the desired futures for the system, 2) experiential knowledge to understand the current concerns in the

system, and 3) practical knowledge to think about strategies that can change the present system to transform to the desired futures. In the first form of knowledge, participants are invited to imagine their desired futures without imposing any previous assumptions to avoid constraining their imaginations about what might be realistically feasible. This form of knowledge is recognized as critical to promoting the identification of potentially key elements for transformative change (Aguilar et al., 2020). The second form of knowledge is based on the participants' experiences, perceptions, and interpretations of the current problems and challenges in the systems that have existed in the past. This form of knowledge is particularly relevant for exploring and identifying patterns within existing systems (Fazey et al., 2020). The third form of knowledge explores realistic pathways to achieve the desired future by building on the current system. This form of knowledge is considered necessary to create tangible strategies on the ground (Buckton et al., 2024).

We built our research upon a knowledge co-production approach—understood as *iterative and collaborative processes involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge, and actors to produce context-specific knowledge and pathways towards a sustainable future* (Norström et al., 2020)—. Acknowledging that literature increasingly recognizes that plural and discordant voices are a constitutive part of sustainability debates and, therefore, should be incorporated (e.g., Anderson et al., 2016; Rawluk et al., 2020), we considered convergent and divergent thinking as an inherent part of our approach. Our research was supported by an iterative and reflective process between the core research team and participants concerning the findings throughout the research. Throughout our research process, we shared results iteratively with participants (via emails and webinars) and asked for their feedback until a consensus was reached. This research approach allowed us to interpret the findings' validity while maintaining participants' attention and engagement on both results and the research process.

2.2. Study area

We focused our study on the Spanish drylands southeast of the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1). This region is the driest area in continental Europe (Armas et al., 2011). It is described as a biodiversity hotspot, with abundant endemism species and priority habitats of interest at the European level (Piñero et al., 2011). Since the 1960s, this region has experienced notable changes mainly derived from the implementation and expansion of intensive and extensive irrigated agriculture—it is one of Europe's most representative agricultural areas called the "Orchard of Europe"—followed by the tourism sector and the construction industry (Grindlay et al., 2011; Sánchez-Picón et al., 2011). This transformation has provided significant benefits in the region through the generation of economic growth and employment. It has also resulted in detrimental environmental changes, including biodiversity loss, due to the increasing pressure on natural resources. This has also brought social consequences like rising inequalities and migration, impacting the structure of local communities (Quintas-Soriano et al., 2016).

From a governance perspective, two regional state administrations, the Autonomous Communities (AC) of Andalucía and Murcia, have primary policy responsibilities in the Spanish drylands region. In addition, there are multiple state administrations at the local scale with governing competencies in this region (i.e., local administrations), which overlap with other governmental bodies at different decision-making scales (e.g., regarding the management of river basins and protected areas). Within the Spanish drylands region, we selected four sites at the regional and local scale. Specifically, we selected the provinces of Almería (AC of Andalucía) and the AC of Murcia as the regional study site, which covers most of the semi-arid ecosystems of the Iberian Peninsula (Armas et al., 2011). Within the regional study site, we selected Campo de Níjar (Almería), Comarca de Los Vélez (Almería), and Campo de Cartagena (Murcia) as the three local study sites, which present particular features and contextual conditions that make them

Fig. 1. Study area. Localization of the four Spanish drylands study sites: one at the regional scale (Almería and Murcia) and three at the local scale (Campo de Níjar, Comarca de Los Vélez, and Campo de Cartagena). Photos by A. Jiménez-Aceituno.

Source of land cover: Map of land use types of the Andalusian region for the year 2007 (Environmental Information Network of Andalusia, www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/site/rediam).

Table 1

Main features and contextual conditions of the four sites that comprise the study area.

Sites	Almería and Murcia	Campo de Níjar	Comarca de Los Vélez	Campo de Cartagena
Scale	Regional	Local	Local	Local
Main administrative units	Province of Almería (AC of Andalucía) and AC of Murcia.	Municipality of Níjar.	Municipalities of Chirivel, María, Vélez Blanco and Vélez Rubio.	Municipalities of Cartagena, Torre-Pacheco, San Pedro del Pinatar, San Javier, La Unión, Los Alcázares, and Fuente Álamo de Murcia.
Economic context	Irrigated agriculture represents the main economic activity in the region, followed by tourism.	It contains the second-largest concentration of greenhouses in the province of Almería dedicated to horticulture production.	It is the largest area of organic almond cultivation in the world. The site also stands out with this production system in legume cereals and fallow land.	It features intensive and extensive irrigated agriculture and urban tourism intensification.
Social dynamic	The agricultural production in the region has attracted many migrant populations, mostly from African countries.	It has high migration rates, especially for African countries, which has led to the establishment of migrant settlements.	The site has gone through some depopulation processes, although establishing a more significant number of foreigners has slowed it down.	The population has increased since the 1990s, related to the arrival of immigrants to work in the construction industry and agriculture (mainly from Africa and South America) or residential tourists (mainly from the EU).
Ecological features	The region supports high levels of biodiversity, with numerous and varied landscapes, housing above all landscapes of Mediterranean scrub, boulevards, and grasslands.	It contains the Cabo de Gata Natural Park, which covers habitats of interest, such as the Mediterranean steppe, dune formations, salt flats, coastal cliffs, and seagrass meadows.	The area contains the Sierra-María Los Vélez Natural Park, with an extensive and well-preserved forest mass of pine trees, unique plant species, and more than one hundred species of birds.	This area contains the Mar Menor Lagoon, One of Europe's largest and most endangered saltwater lagoons. The lagoon has suffered an ecological collapse mostly from its management and the implications of surrounding agriculture.
Human impacts	Natural resources overexploitation (aquifers), contamination of other water sources, and land-use changes.	Pressure on aquifers, causing serious availability and quality problems and land-use changes.	Deforestation, impacts on aquifers by overexploitation, and land use transformation regarding the introduction of ecological almond tree plantations.	The eutrophic crisis in the Mar Menor Lagoon provoked the disappearance of the seabed meadows, the depletion of oxygen and the death of numerous organisms, natural resources overexploitation, and land-use changes.
Major sustainability tensions	Declaration of competing interests between conservation actions and economic development.	The intensive agricultural model is based on the labor force from migrants and is in conflict with conservation actions linked to the Cabo de Gata-Níjar Natural Park.	Commodities exports versus local food security versus biodiversity loss versus water for irrigation.	Social tensions around how the Mar Menor Lagoon should be governed.
References	Sánchez-Picón et al., 2011; Castro et al., 2019	Quintas-Soriano et al., 2016; Fradejas-García et al., 2024	Alba-Patiño et al., 2021; López-Felices et al., 2023	Álvarez-Rogel et al., 2020; Bernabé-Crespo et al., 2021

suitable for comparative analysis (Fig. 1). The description of the four study sites is detailed in Table 1. Our selection was founded on the assumptions that 1) locally-based governance is crucial for the successful implementation of SDGs related initiatives, and 2) encompassing multiple geographical regions and scales is key to overcoming the challenges posed by the intersection of multiple governing competencies and the existence of non-state actors with various interests and perspectives in a particular area (Jiménez-Aceituno et al., 2020; Ningrum et al., 2023).

2.3. Methods

2.3.1. Workshop design and data collection

We conducted four in-person 3H-CLD workshops (1.5 days each) at each study site (June, July, and November 2022). Before the 3H-CLD workshops, we conducted several informal meetings with key informants to start identifying representative actors in the Spanish drylands region by applying the snowball technique (Bernard, 2006). Then, we invited the representative actors (n = 38) to participate in five online workshops to co-create maps of the relevant actors' network in the social-ecological dynamic of each site (more details in López-Rodríguez et al., 2024). As a result, we identified 252 actors from different groups (e.g., state administrations, universities, education centers, non-profit organizations, private companies, and local communities) for the four sites. Each identified actor was situated within the corresponding site. We established a balanced representation of 100 actors for the regional site and 50 actors for each local site. Due to economic and human

resources constraints, the maximum number of people we planned to have in each workshop was 50 for the regional site and 30 for the local sites. For each workshop, we initially invited a balanced sample of actors from all groups adapted to the maximum of participants. We ended up inviting a total of 252 actors [Almería and Murcia (n≈102), Campo de Níjar (n≈50), Comarca de Los Vélez (n≈50), Campo de Cartagena (n≈50)]. We invited the identified actors to participate in the four 3H-CLD workshops by email and phone call, balancing the sample of actors from the different identified groups for each workshop. However, only 59 actors from different groups accepted our invitation, and those were the participants who finally attended the workshops [Almería and Murcia (n = 14), Campo de Níjar (n = 15), Comarca de Los Vélez (n = 13), Campo de Cartagena (n = 17)] (Appendix A). We obtained informed consent from each participant to take photos and audio-record participants' interventions before each 3H-CLD workshop.

The design of the workshops followed the 3H-CLD approach (Aguiar et al., under review), which represents an adapted and evolved version of the initial 3H4SDG approach (Aguiar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023). The 3H-CLD is a multi-scale participatory approach that combines the 3H framework with innovative techniques such as system thinking tools (e.g., CLD and the Seeds of Good Anthropocene) and arts-based activities (e.g., theatre of the oppressed techniques) to engage multiple actors in visioning pathways to sustainable futures (Aguiar et al., under review). All methodological details concerning the whole 3H-CLD approach are described in Aguiar et al. (under review). In this article, we describe the methodological aspects concerning the part of the 3H-CLD approach

Fig. 2. Illustration of the 3H diagram and the three steps (adapted from Collste et al., 2023). a) Illustrations of the sequential steps followed to develop the part of the 3H-CLD approach that is aimed to develop the 3H framework in the workshops: Step 1 (Desired futures) and Step 2 (Current concerns) using the color sticky notes system to collect participants' ideas according to the four dimensions of the SDGs (i.e., social, economic, environmental, and governance), and Step 3 (Strategies to achieve the desired futures) utilizing blue sticky notes. b) Illustration of the 3H diagram resulting from developing the 3 Steps. The pictures show an example of the 3H diagram built on the wall and participants working in groups during the workshops. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

that is aimed to develop the 3H framework in our study sites since it provided the required data to respond to our research goal that is focused on examining the potential of the 3H-CLD approach for supporting policy coherence at multiple governance scales for SDG implementation. As part of the 3H-CLD approach, the 3H framework is framed in a diagram with a Y-axis representing the level of dominance of the features in the analyzed system and an X-axis representing time (see Sharpe et al., 2016). Within these two axes, the 3H framework is built through collective thinking in three sequential steps aimed at identifying a) elements that define desired future visions for 2040–2050 (Step 1), b) current concerns that may hinder the desired future visions (Step 2), and c) strategies to achieve the desired future visions (Step 3) (Fig. 2a).

All the 3H-CLD workshops were supported by a team of three facilitators responsible for moderating and facilitating them, as well as note-takers and technical assistants. They received training on the 3H-CLD approach and workshop dynamics before each workshop. All the workshops followed the same structure. We started by briefly presenting the XPaths project as a science-action process with different phases (clarifying that the 3H-CLD workshops constituted an intermediate phase of such process and the results would serve as input to further workshops focused on co-creating an action plan to advance in SDG implementation in the region), research goals, study sites (clarifying the site and scale on which each workshop would be focused), workshop agenda, and workshop operation mode. The last involved a collective arrangement by including facilitators' and participants' commitments to workshop functioning based on a horizontal structure to avoid power imbalances and ensure a warm, safe, and caring work environment that facilitates common understanding (Appendix B). At this point, we explained that workshops would be based on a knowledge co-production approach in which convergent and divergent thinking would be considered an inherent part. Therefore, both perspectives could be recognized and embraced throughout the deliberative processes. We divided participants into two heterogeneous groups (6–8 people per group) and involved a facilitator and a note-taker in each group. To frame the ideas exchange and collective deliberation among participants, we used the 3H diagram (Fig. 2a) drawn on a paper poster on the wall, and we defined the following overarching questions for each step: *What are your desired visions for the future of your site in 2040–2050?* (Step 1: desired futures); *What concerns do you have about the present system on your site?* (Step 2: current concerns); and, *How do we change the present system to transform to the desired future?* and *Which strategies are required?* (strategies can encompass both the implementation of new initiatives and the expansion of existing ones; these strategies aim to contribute to achieving elements of the desired futures or address the concerns identified in previous steps) (Step 3: strategies to achieve the desired futures). The workshop dynamics were conducted as described in Collste et al. (2023). To develop Steps 1 and 2, the facilitators invited participants to link their ideas to four dimensions of the SDGs using specific colored sticky notes: social dimension (SDGs 1–6, pink color), economic dimension (SDGs 7–12, yellow color), environmental dimension (SDGs 13–15, green color), and, governance dimension (SDGs 16–17, orange color) (Fig. 2b). This color system helped participants to think, propose, and discuss their ideas in terms of the SDGs framework. We provided paper cards with the SDGs and a summary of the SDGs framework to be used by participants as complementary material to support this activity. Then, for Step 3, we used blue sticky notes to answer the question concerning strategies to move from the present to the desired futures (Fig. 2b). The note-takers used a predefined template to gather the sticky notes for the three steps, as well as the minutes of the collective discussions, the photos with the results of each step and general comments and observations concerning the workshop dynamics (e.g., participation patterns, tensions between participants and potential misunderstandings). Furthermore, all interventions and collective deliberations were audio-recorded. After each workshop, each facilitator and note-taker met to complete the data collection template. Coffee breaks and lunches were organized during the workshops to promote

participants' informal meetings and networking and provide them with moments of rest. We developed preliminary reports with the outcomes for each workshop and sent them to participants by email, allowing them to incorporate corrections and suggestions. Then, after receiving their feedback, we developed final reports that were sent again to participants by email, inviting them to opine about the introduced changes and make new comments and suggestions if needed. After that, the final reports were disseminated (e.g., via email and webinar) and published on the project website to make them publicly accessible.

2.3.2. Data analysis

2.3.2.1. Content analysis. We summarized 787 participants' ideas (sticky notes) from four workshops: 354 ideas on desired futures, 257 on current concerns, and 176 on sustainability strategies (Appendix C, Table C1). These were complemented with insights from individual interventions and group deliberations collected by note-takers (Walford, 2009). Photos and audio files were consulted to clarify participants' perceptions when needed.

First, qualitative data was analyzed by examining all these ideas through content analysis (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005), focusing on identifying convergences and divergences between workshop groups. Divergent ideas were interpreted as concurrence of opinions, while divergent ideas included differing views about the same topic (Appendix C, Table C2). Second, we applied an inductive content analysis (Newing, 2010) to group the examined ideas into themes based on content similarity. Each theme included the ideas that participants mentioned in each workshop, their absolute frequencies, and, when applicable, divergences associated (Appendix D). Third, we classified the identified themes according to the four dimensions of the SDGs (i.e., social, economic, environmental, and governance) and the SDGs whose content had a closer relationship. Two researchers analyzed and reviewed the identified themes and their connections to the SDGs to ensure consistency and accuracy.

2.3.2.2. Descriptive statistics. Coherence in SDG implementation calls for identifying critical themes to harmonize policy priorities and align actions across governance scales and areas through agreements between state and non-state actors (Lieu et al., 2018). Under this assumption, firstly, we focused on developing a comparative analysis across sites to determine themes that 1) could be considered relatively context-independent and be used as a common ground between sites (i.e., similar themes) and 2) proved to be highly relevant in some sites and relatively dependently from their specific contexts (i.e., dissimilar themes). To do that, we first compared the absolute frequencies associated with the participants' ideas grouped by themes (Appendix E, Table E1 and E2). We second used descriptive statistics to identify similar and dissimilar themes across sites regarding the desired futures and current concerns. Specifically, we established a threshold to identify themes with an absolute frequency higher than the average. We calculated the average using 1000 bootstrap samples (Efron and Tibshirani, 1994) gathered from the total number of ideas contributed by participants across all sites. We considered a "similar theme" across sites when it had a non-zero absolute frequency in all sites and a "dissimilar theme" when it exceeded the average in some sites but had an absolute frequency of zero in others. Secondly, we examined potential associations between themes concerning the strategies to achieve the desired futures across the four sites, from local to regional scales. To achieve this, we analyzed the resultant themes in Step 3, using their absolute frequencies (Appendix E, Table E3) to build a Sankey diagram. This allowed us to pinpoint common areas for coordinating actions across sites and scales.

Throughout the data analysis process with qualitative and quantitative techniques, we (the authors)—with direct knowledge of the study area, skilled in the 3H framework, and involved in the workshops—hold collective meetings to check the rigor of data analysis and discuss the

results in each step of the process. Our context-based knowledge in the study area helped us to interpret the elicited knowledge and perspectives from the workshops and triangulated data with previous studies in the case study area (e.g., Castro et al., 2019) in order to understand if it was well-suited to support policy coherence in the study area context (Fazey et al., 2018).

2.3.2.3. Reflective practice. Reflective practice about the experiential knowledge gained using the 3H framework is relevant to facilitating its use and supporting transformative change toward sustainability (Sharpe et al., 2016; Fazey et al., 2020). With this goal in mind, we held sequenced discussions (one after each 3H-CLD workshop) to deliberate about the main positive aspects and limitations of the methodological approach we adopted. The results were summarized in a template. We also revised the data collected by note-takers during the workshops to identify inputs from workshop participants on the approach and outcomes. The summaries and workshop notes were analyzed through qualitative content analysis (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005) by looking at representative perceptions.

3. Results

3.1. Desired futures

3.1.1. Similarities for the desired futures across sites and divergences associated

Regarding the similar themes (i.e., themes relatively context-independent and conceived as a common ground between sites), we found 12 themes about the desired futures among the sites (Fig. 3) and four divergences associated with them (Appendix D, Table D4). These 12 themes were identified from an initial list of 31 themes for the desired futures (Appendix D and E). All SDGs were addressed by the identified similar themes of desired futures except SDG 1 (No poverty) and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) (Appendix D).

Of these 12 similar future themes identified across sites, 33 % referred to subjects associated with the economic dimension of the SDGs (e.g., achieving a sustainable production framework and the diversification of economic activities), 33 % to the social dimension (e.g., promoting education for sustainability and social equality), 25 % to the governance dimension (e.g., implementing coherent policies for sustainable development and facilitating public participation), and 9 % to the environmental dimension by referring to the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystems (Fig. 3). The most mentioned future-themes by participants included the desire to achieve a sustainable production framework ($n = 48$), conserving biodiversity and ecosystems ($n = 29$), implementing coherent policies for sustainable development ($n = 26$), and promoting education for sustainability ($n = 22$) (Appendix E).

Overall, participants in all the sites emphasized the need to adopt a sustainable production framework that can create goods and services that are socially beneficial, economically viable, and environmentally friendly. They especially underscored the importance of transforming the current agricultural system, the primary economic activity in all the study sites, since they perceived that it currently finds itself in a crisis of diminishing economic benefits and increasing environmental and social dilemmas. Participants envisioned a future with an agricultural system focused on producing high-quality ecological products and adopting sustainability as a market brand. In this sense, three divergent perspectives emerged (Appendix D). First, some participants posed the dilemma of reducing the greenhouses and crop extension in the future vs. putting effort into sustainability efficiency for the intensive agriculture sector (while keeping the current extension) (Appendix D; Table D4, D4). This divergence also led to the emergence of other perspectives around the debate about whether or not organic agriculture could be considered more sustainable than ecological agriculture (Appendix D; Table D4, D2). The third divergent perspective encompassed

whether or not to create alternative networks to the current cooperatives and companies that distribute agricultural products in the region (Appendix D; Table D4, D1). In addition, participants expressed the desire to evolve toward a more sustainable tourism sector (particularly in coastal areas) that can prevent massification and prioritize nature's protection.

Beyond current agricultural and tourism practices, participants desired a future socio-economic model that would diversify economic activities, including ecological agriculture, ecotourism, and other telework activities, all developed sustainably. They also highlighted that the future socio-economic model should ensure social integration, cohesion, and cohabitation among individuals and communities, and compatibility with the conservation of biodiversity and ecosystems by preventing environmental degradation and implementing an integrated and sustainable spatial planning that contributes to the connectivity between urban and rural areas and among protected areas.

Participants also expressed their desire for integrated policies that are coherent and adapted to the local and regional context. These policies should facilitate and ensure sustainability in response to specific challenges (e.g., rural abandonment, environmental degradation, and water overexploitation). They envisioned the development of such policies through public institutions promoting democratic participation and providing mechanisms for inclusive governance that enhances public participation, involvement in decision-making, and social engagement. Furthermore, participants emphasized the need to establish strong and transparent institutions, ensure public resource availability and equitable distribution, and implement effective political leadership to achieve the 2030 Agenda goals.

For the future, participants also highlighted the need for an educational system that would increase awareness about the notion of sustainability in all its dimensions. They stressed the importance of including sustainability education in formal education at all levels, and in combination with non-formal learning experiences, to contribute to developing sustainability competencies among students. However, some participants disagreed about the role that non-formal education should play in the future compared to formal ones (Appendix D; Table D4, D5). Also, participants envisioned that the desired educational system could also contribute to advancing social justice by promoting principles of equality, inclusion and diversity for all people. They also highlighted the necessity of ensuring basic services (e.g., education, housing, decent work, water, and health) to improve the quality of life of the local population.

Finally, participants pointed out the need for an integrated and efficient water management system that prevents deterioration and overexploitation of water ecosystems (e.g., aquifers and lagoons) to secure the future water supply to the population. Likewise, they stressed the importance of considering the region's water balance and integrating other water resources sustainably (e.g., groundwater, desalinated water, and wastewater). The conservation of biodiversity and dryland ecosystems was also seen as essential for a sustainable future. Participants gave special attention to the preservation and improvement of protected areas and the restoration of degraded ecosystems. In this regard, they also highlighted the need to make collective efforts toward sustainable use of natural resources.

3.1.2. Dissimilarities for the desired futures across sites and divergences associated

Regarding dissimilar themes for the desired futures across the sites (i.e., themes highly relevant in some sites and thus relatively dependent on their specific contexts), we found seven themes (out of a total of 31 themes) (Fig. 3; Appendix D and E) that presented one divergence associated (Appendix D, Table D4). The seven dissimilar future themes involved matters associated with two dimensions of the SDGs in two sites: Campo de Níjar and Campo de Cartagena. Specifically, 86 % of these themes referred to subjects related to the economic dimension (e.g., fostering efficient waste management and circular economy, and sustainable consumption patterns) and 14 % to the governance

Fig. 3. Themes for the desired futures and current concerns were identified in the four study sites during the workshops. Themes are grouped by the four dimensions of the SDGs (i.e., economic, environmental, governance, and social) and linked to the SDGs which are closely connected to each theme [SDGs: (2) Zero Hunger; (3) Good Health and Well-being; (4) Quality Education; (5) Gender Equality; (6) Clean Water and Sanitation; (7) Affordable and Clean Energy; (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth; (10) Reduced Inequality; (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities; (12) Responsible Consumption and Production; (13) Climate Action; (14) Life Below Water; (15) Life on Land; (16) Peace and Justice Strong Institutions; (17) Partnerships to achieve the Goals]. The bars represent the number of participants' ideas (in absolute frequencies) associated with each theme. Similar themes are identified with triangles and dissimilar themes with asterisks. The dashed line represents the average of participants' ideas across sites.

dimension (i.e., enhancing alliances between public and private sectors and promoting collective action networks). The dissimilar themes for the desired futures established links with 6 SDGs [(7) Affordable and Clean Energy; (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth; (10) Reduced Inequality; (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities; (12) Responsible Consumption and Production; and (17) Partnerships to achieve the Goals].

In Campo de Níjar, workshop participants highly mentioned that achieving a sustainable future requires an efficient waste management system that promotes implementing a circular bioeconomy model. On this issue, participants posed a divergence around whether agriculture can be (or not) conceived as a source for capturing carbon (Appendix D; Table D4, D3). They also preferred to adopt an energy system based on renewable energies in the future compared with the rest of the sites. Moreover, these participants particularly stressed the need for a sustainable future that includes decent work conditions, assurance of labor rights opportunities, and guaranteed access to housing, especially for minority groups such as migrants and young people.

In Campo de Cartagena, workshop participants highly mentioned the need for a change in the economic model, emphasizing the importance of local production and a social shift in consumption patterns to prioritize the purchase of locally produced and sold products in the area. In addition, they significantly mentioned the need to apply an equitable wealth distribution. Further, participants often mentioned that the desired future needs to improve coordination between public administrations and other social sectors. They also highlighted the need to generate alliances at different scales to advance the achievement of the SDGs.

3.2. Current concerns

3.2.1. Similarities for the current concerns across sites and divergences associated

Regarding the similar themes related to the current concerns, we found 15 themes across the sites (out of a total of 31 themes) (Fig. 3; Appendix D and E) and six divergences associated with them (Appendix D, Table D4). The identified similar themes associated with current concerns also established links with all SDGs except SDG 1 (No poverty) and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) (Appendix D). By comparing the identified similar themes for the desired futures and the current concerns, we found a high correspondence in terms of complementarity between them, meaning that the envisioned themes for the future matched current preoccupations.

The 47 % of these similar themes applied to a variety of economic related-issues (e.g., the existence of an unsustainable production framework and lack of support for local economies and large companies competitors), 27 % referred to governance concerns (e.g., the actual presence of inefficient institutions and lack of political leadership for sustainability, and absence of coherent policies for sustainability), 13 % to environmental and social problems, respectively, such as the presence of drivers of global change that generate environmental impacts and the existence of social inequalities (Fig. 3). The most mentioned concern-themes were focused on the presence of inefficient institutions and lack of political leadership for sustainability ($n = 28$), the existence of an unsustainable consumption framework ($n = 20$), the inefficient management of migratory flows and population dynamics ($n = 19$), and the increasing pressure of drivers of global change on nature ($n = 18$) (Appendix E).

The most relevant concern shared by participants in all the sites was the presence of governmental institutions led by politicians who needed more leadership to transform the current system toward sustainability. They perceived politicians often adopt short-term thinking and perspectives disconnected from social realities. They thought the latest led to the limited availability of public resources to ensure compliance with legislation and the need for updated and contextualized policies and plans that balance the economy, society, and environment in

coordination between public administrations. Participants also emphasized the need for more institutional mechanisms that promote governance modes involving society and the lack of participatory culture in the local population, which act as disabling factors to promote cooperation between public and private sectors in addressing sustainability challenges collectively. In this regard, some participants diverged about the lack of social activism in the region (Appendix D; Table D4, D12) and others about whether the private sector exercised power on particular public administrations (Appendix D; Table D4, D11).

Among their concerns, participants also highlighted that they perceived the current intensive agricultural production system as unsustainable, with economic growth exceeding ecological boundaries. Here, they expressed two divergences around to which extent the agricultural system could be considered efficient regarding resource use and whether conversion of unirrigated zones into irrigated land through formal authorization is maintained (Appendix D; Table D4, D8, and D10). They also showed concern about the lack of support for local economies and the intense competition with large companies. In particular, they emphasized the vulnerability of the agricultural model due to its reliance on external factors, such as price volatility and raw materials provided by external companies. They perceived large companies exhibiting little concern and engagement with locals, identifying the lack of subsidies to support small farmers economically.

In addition, participants expressed concerns about the economic stagnation and loss of purchasing power caused by economic crisis, inflation, and the loss of economic profitability of both the agriculture and tourism sectors. They diverged about whether the current economic model is generating poverty in the study area (Appendix D; Table D4, D9). Participants also expressed concern about the limited diversification of economic activities in the case study, which results in a highly dependence on the intensive agricultural model and tourism activities.

Participants also expressed concern about precarious working conditions in all sectors (especially the agricultural sector) significantly impacting vulnerable groups (e.g., migrants, women, and young people). In this regard, they stressed the inefficient management of migratory flows and population dynamics, which, in turn, leads to social tensions between locals and migrants in search of work and a better life, hindering the social integration and cohesion among the local population, and to the abandonment of rural areas generating aging population, lack of generational replacement and talent drain. Participants also expressed concern regarding social inequalities in all the sites. They particularly emphasized the disparities faced by minority groups, including migrants, women, young people, and rural populations, in terms of access to social rights, salaries, and basic services such as housing.

Given the semi-arid nature of the region, most participants were also concerned about the scarcity of water resources and the existence of a water management system managed by large companies that may hinder access to water in the future. They perceived that the current water system relied on an unlimited extraction of water resources (generating mainly overexploitation and pollution in aquifers) and water distribution inequalities. The shared perception is that this level of water scarcity will increase, negatively impacting people's health and productivity and threatening biodiversity, ecosystems, and sustainable development.

Finally, participants also expressed concerns regarding the multiple global change drivers occurring in the region. These drivers were overexploitation of natural resources, with particular emphasis on water resources, land use changes, soil degradation, pollution, climate change, and invasive species. They identified these factors as leading to biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation. There were divergent opinions about whether or not the past forest management also led to biodiversity loss (Appendix D; Table D4, D7).

3.2.2. Dissimilarities for the current concerns across sites and divergences associated

Regarding dissimilar themes, we found two themes for current concerns across the sites (out of a total of 31 themes) (Fig. 3; Appendix D and E) that presented one divergence associated (Appendix D, Table D4). One hundred percent of them referred to social-related issues in Comarca de Los Vélez and Campo de Cartagena (i.e., human-nature disconnection and the need for information for sustainability). The dissimilar themes for the current concerns established links with the SDG (4) Quality Education (Appendix D).

In Comarca de Los Vélez and Campo de Cartagena, human-nature disconnection caused recurring concerns among workshop

participants. Human-nature disconnection was associated with the lack of social awareness regarding human dependence on nature and was perceived as a significant barrier to implementing the SDGs. Here, workshop participants showed divergent perspectives about whether or not assigning an instrumental value to natural resources is required for nature conservation (Appendix D; Table D4, D6).

In Campo de Cartagena, workshop participants also expressed deep concerns about the need for reliable information to progress toward sustainability. They significantly perceived the absence of reliable and truthful information on the environmental impacts caused by economic activities and their consequences on the population's health as a barrier to progress in implementing the SDGs (Appendix D).

Fig. 4. Associations between themes concerning the strategies to achieve the desired futures between the different sites and scales. Themes are described according to their absolute frequency (i.e., the number of participants' ideas) for the different sites and scales. Each theme's different range of colors is associated with the different dimensions of the SDGs (i.e., social, economic, environmental, and governance).

3.3. Strategies to achieve the desired futures: Associations between themes across sites and scales

We found 19 themes that grouped strategies to achieve the desired futures with the potential to establish different types of associations between the different sites and at different scales (Fig. 4). Through these themes, we distinguished 11 divergences (Appendix D, Table D4). These 19 themes were identified from an initial list of 23 themes (Appendix D and E).

Fifty-eight percent of the themes included strategies that addressed issues associated with the economic dimension of the SDGs (e.g., enhancing waste management and production framework), 21 % with the governance (e.g., fostering alliances between public and private sectors and collective actions networks and policy coherence for sustainable development), 16 % with the social (e.g., education and information for sustainability), and finally 5 % with the environmental (i.e., conserving biodiversity and ecosystems). These themes established links with 11 SDGs: (4) Quality Education; (6) Clean Water and Sanitation; (7) Affordable and Clean Energy; (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth; (10) Reduced Inequality; (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities; (12) Responsible Consumption and Production; (14) Life Below Water; (15) Life on Land; (16) Peace and Justice Strong Institutions; (17) Partnerships to achieve the Goals (Appendix D).

Among the 19 identified themes, six of them emerged in all sites, holding the potential to establish associations between strategies at the regional scale and the three local sites (Appendix E). Of these six themes, 33 % covered strategies intended to address social challenges, such as implementing the SDGs cross-cuttingly in the curricular itinerary of the different educational levels and developing awareness programs on sustainability in all actor groups and sectors. Another 33 % of the strategies were focused on dealing with governance issues, for instance, creating alliances with supermarkets to avoid throwing away food and beverages and agreements with the agricultural sector and local restaurants and markets to promote the consumption of local products. Seventeen percent of the strategies were aimed at coping with economic and environmental trials, respectively. Examples of strategies associated with the economic dimension included the distribution of cloth bags in local markets and the implementation of compost bins in towns. Restoration of ecosystems to prevent forest fires and plans for reducing water erosion were some examples of strategies in the environmental dimension.

In addition, we found eight themes that included strategies with the potential to support associations between the regional scale and one or two of the sites at the local scale (Appendix E). Seventy-five percent of these themes covered strategies, for example, to improve the planning, connections, and territorial integration, production framework, energy system, labor market, management of migratory and population dynamics, and social rights and opportunities. Twenty-five percent of the themes included strategies to enhance governance, such as creating socially inclusive participatory mechanisms based on collective reflection and collaborative work and implementing social incentives to encourage population involvement in participatory processes.

Regarding associations between sites at the local scale, we found five themes that included different strategies with the potential to set up synergies. Eight percent covered themes associated with economic issues, for instance, the creation of incentives to visualize sustainability practices in agriculture and the promotion of a network of local food markets. Twenty percent of the strategies focused on well-informed societies through improving the transfer of scientific knowledge on sustainability issues with local communities. The remaining four themes included specific strategies linked to only one site (i.e., housing, wealth distribution, diversification of economic activities, and consumption framework).

3.4. Reflections on methodology

We found that the 3H-CLD approach in the workshops provided a structured method to deliberate on the desired futures, current concerns, and strategies to achieve the desired futures in the context of the SDGs at the local and regional scales. On this basis, we identified three main aspects associated with the methodological approach we adopted: the SDG framework, the adoption of convergent and divergent thinking, and the workshops' outcomes.

Organizing the deliberations under the SDG framework facilitated participants to think, propose, and discuss their ideas in terms of the four dimensions of the SDGs (i.e., social, economic, environmental, and governance). This helped participants to think about sustainability in an integrated way, establishing connections between elements of the different dimensions. However, we also identified two limitations regarding the application of the SDG framework. One limitation referred to the classification of ideas in the different SDG dimensions since some ideas could be associated with various dimensions, generating confusion among certain participants. The other limitation was associated with participants' predefined conceptions of the SDG framework. We found different perspectives in this regard. For instance, we identified that most participants perceived the SDG framework as an opportunity to progress toward sustainability globally and supported implementing local and regional initiatives in connection with it. However, we also found that several participants conceived the 2030 Agenda as a global instrument hardly embedded into the institutional settings at the sub-global scales, which made its operationalization challenging in the regional and local realities. In addition, a few participants showed a critical position toward the 2030 Agenda because they considered it to continue to promote economic growth, showing skepticism about how it could help achieve sustainable development in real terms.

Acknowledging convergent and divergent thinking as an inherent part of the workshops, and thus, recognizing and embracing both perspectives throughout the deliberative processes, helped us facilitate constructive discussions in an environment where all voices can be heard and considered while fostering the exchange of information and learning between participants. We identified that participants showed a progressive, proactive, and trusting interaction throughout the workshops based on a constructive dialogue around the area's future and how to transform it to advance toward sustainability. In this regard, participants showed high positive satisfaction with the dialogue based on recognizing convergent and divergent thinking. They expressed that it had facilitated active listening and respect between different perspectives despite no agreement on specific issues and expressed interest in maintaining the dialogue platform in the long term.

Contextualizing the 3H-CLD approach as part of a broad science-action process, focused on co-creating an integrated action plan to progress in SDG implementation in the study area, helped participants conceive the workshops' outcomes as *intermediate results* that formed part of a wider process. From the beginning, we assumed that the workshop outcomes (i.e., themes concerning the desired futures, current challenges, and strategies to achieve the desired futures) would need to be integrated through a cross-scale analysis in connection with SDGs. This analysis allowed us to identify themes to harmonize policy priorities and associations between strategies that might support policy coherence for SDG implementation in the study area. We used these results as input in subsequent workshops to determine strategic lines of action from a multi-scale governance perspective and then define them in terms of tasks, the scale of implementation, resources, and actors who might be involved (beyond the scope of this study). The latter workshops also formed part of the science-action process mentioned above to co-create an integrated action plan for SDG implementation in the study area. These clarifications concerning the outcomes from the 3H-CLD workshops helped to prevent participants' perceptions and expectations of the workshops from generating isolated results that could be directly implemented; instead, they conceived as baseline outcomes of a

broad science-action process, in which their participation and engagement would be needed to achieve the goal of the mentioned science-action process. On this basis, we clarified through the workshops that the research team would elaborate on the outcomes and present them to participants (via webinar and email), asking for their feedback to be input in subsequent workshops.

4. Discussion

4.1. Harmonizing policy priorities to support policy coherence in SDG implementation

Implementing the 2030 Agenda depends mainly on the ability of policymakers and actors to develop coherent policies with coordinated and harmonized sustainability targets across sites and scales (Ashoff, 2005; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016; Lieu et al., 2018). However, policies are often designed and implemented by various isolated government bodies across many sectors and scales, with differences in understanding of what sustainable development means (Counsell, 1999). This often leads to unintended outcomes due to contradicting policy objectives that can hinder advancement toward sustainability (OECD, 2007; Ross and Dovers, 2008; Lieu et al., 2018). Our findings show two ways the 3H-CLD can support policy coherence in implementing the SDGs. On the one hand, the approach helped to reveal multiple similar themes between sites that showed a high level of agreement about some of the elements that shape the sustainable future participants want and common concerns that need to be addressed to achieve it (Fig. 3; Appendix E, Table E1). These themes are in line with what Castro et al. (2019) identified in a previous study focusing on determining collective challenges for supporting the sustainability transformation of the agricultural sector in the region. We argue that the identified themes through dialogue between actors from multiple sectors could serve as common ground to align overarching policy targets consistently from a multi-scale governance perspective. An example is the participants' agreement on the need for public institutions to promote democratic participation and provide participatory mechanisms that enhance social involvement in decision-making for sustainability. It is widely recognized that sustainability requires the creation of social spaces based on co-learning and collective work instead of the negotiation of individual interests and preferences (Rist et al., 2007). In Spain, as in many other countries, most institutional mechanisms shaping decision-making are based on consultative approaches that do not fully enable social actors from different groups to work together in pathways to sustainability (e.g., advisory boards and coordination bodies). Public administrations in the region have not contemplated an effective model to involve social actors in public participation through the co-creation and co-implementation of initiatives to progress toward sustainability (Castro et al., 2019). The convergence of participants in transforming the participatory spaces in the region provides social support for policymakers in addressing institutional changes.

On the other hand, the 3H-CLD approach contributed to identifying several dissimilar themes that revealed relevant contextual realities within the region. These highly context-specific themes are also recognized as fundamental to developing coherent policies for implementing the SDGs and, therefore, need to be addressed (e.g., Weitz et al., 2018; Odume et al., 2021). For instance, in Campo de Níjar local site, participants frequently mentioned that sustainable futures of the area should be founded on decent work and labor conditions. Contextual factors can explain this vision. From the 1980s to the present, this area has suffered intensive agricultural development, which has been increasingly supported by low-income and seasonal jobs, mainly held by migrants from Africa (Roquero, 1996). Many of these migrants live in extremely precarious conditions (Pumares, 2003), suffering labor segmentation and residential segregation in isolated and substandard settlements (Checa Olmos and Arjona Garrido, 2007; Bonillo et al., 2011; Pumares Fernández, 2012; Rouland, 2014). Participants underscored how these

factors have generated multiple social tensions and highlighted that they must be addressed to ensure sustainability in Campo de Níjar. This theme, however, received less attention in the rest of the workshops, suggesting its strong contextual dependence.

4.2. Establishing associations among strategies to assist coordinated actions across areas and scales

Developing coordinated strategies that connect the needs and agendas across regions and scales is also considered a key step for establishing collaboration among institutions and actors (Ross and Dovers, 2008; Edelenbos and Van Meerkerk, 2018) that helps drive coherent action for progressing to SDG implementation (Aguiar et al., 2020; Downing et al., 2021). Our results show different types of associations that can be established between the strategies identified across study sites and scales that can contribute to facilitating the articulation and coordination of collective actions in alignment with the 2030 Agenda. An illustrative example is the strategies focused on enhancing education for sustainability (Appendix D). These strategies were considered fundamental to achieving the SDGs in all the sites, requiring the integration of institutional and societal efforts from diverse sectors (e.g., public administration, educational, academic, social, and cultural) and across scales (e.g., local and regional) (Appendix E, Table E3). For example, these strategies proposed structural reforms of the educational system at different scales and under the competence of the regional government; capacity-building educational courses for all sectors (i.e., agriculture, tourism, industry) promoted by both educational centers and universities; as well as experiential learning programs promoted by grassroots initiatives and cultural institutions (Appendix D, Table D3). Concurrently, the results also reveal other associations that could be established between local and regional strategies and thus implemented in coordination with actors at different scales. Examples are the strategies for managing the migratory and population dynamics and promoting social rights and opportunities proposed in Campo de Níjar to provide solutions for minority groups (e.g., migrants and the young population). Whereas these strategies would require guidance and support from the local government to be implemented, they could also be launched by aligning them with the strategies on these themes defined at the regional scale. Acknowledging that finding potential areas for collaboration can support the establishment of practical agreements for taking joint action for sustainability (López-Rodríguez et al., 2023), we argue that identified associations in the strategies proposed across sites and scales might constitute focal points where diverse actors can focus efforts. Therefore, policymakers and practitioners could use them to align interests, goals, and resources between actors and sectors and create collective action networks to promote joint strategic actions.

4.3. Implications for the 3H-CLD practice

This section stresses the main positive aspects and limitations of the 3H-CLD approach we adopted. One of the main characteristics of the approach is that it adapts the 3H framework to the context of SDGs. As such, when applying it, the dialogues and deliberations are guided under the SDG framework, which offers some advantages but also presents challenges. As stated for the original 3H4SDG approach (Aguiar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023), the 3H-CLD facilitated a holistic and integrated exploration of the pathways to the SDGs by steering clear of isolated discussions on individual goals or groups of goals. In addition, we found that it provided opportunities to develop in-depth deliberations and pathways to establish connections between regional and local scenarios with the SDGs. This is a relevant aspect since the necessity of connecting and integrating these global sustainability goals with multiple governance scales, especially locally, in which many initiatives occur, is recognized as a remaining challenge in SDG implementation (Jiménez-Aceituno et al., 2020). However, we also find one challenge when classifying ideas into the dimensions of the SDGs by

specific actors who needed clarification since the ideas might cover various dimensions. To clarify this, we explained that ideas could be classified in the dimensions they considered more appropriate, highlighting that narratives behind the ideas were more important than the classification itself. Another challenge was the disparities in conceptions and opinions regarding the SDG framework (especially opponents). To address it throughout the workshops, we explained that the SDG framework would be used as an “umbrella” to organize deliberations and think in pathways toward sustainability in an integrated way on the basis that it currently represents the current global instrument that offers the practical chance to establish connections with local and regional pathways to progress toward sustainability in the real world. In line with this, for future studies, we suggest clarifying from the beginning of the workshops that the SDG framework is used to guide discussions about sustainability in a broad sense as a starting point to envision local and regional pathways in connection with it.

In line with Aguiar et al. (2020) and Collste et al. (2023), we also identified that the 3H-CLD helped to integrate multiple values and knowledge systems from diverse actors and captured convergent and divergent perspectives. Literature increasingly advocates for incorporating a variety of perspectives that reflect different ontological assumptions and epistemological viewpoints in sustainability debates since plural and discordant voices are a constitutive part of it (e.g., Anderson et al., 2016; Rawluk et al., 2020). Previous studies suggest that social processes with divergent perspectives provide opportunities to 1) foster dialogue that allows for reflection and learning about the complexities of social-ecological systems, 2) build consensual solutions, 3) allow dissenting visions to surface tensions or conflicts that need to be addressed, and 4) to use dissent to open up new possibilities for more transformative action (Raymond et al., 2022; Rawluk et al., 2020). Specifically, we identified that the 3H-CLD contributed to emerging dissent that opened the possibility of gaining a new understanding of what sustainability themes mean for different actors while still allowing participants to seek consensual ideas to advance toward sustainability. For example, participants showed agreement on the need to transform the agriculture production system. However, they diverged on how to achieve that: whether to limit the surface of agriculture in the future or put effort into sustainability efficiency for the intensive agriculture sector. This illustrated the need to develop further and in-depth discussions through social deliberations to co-define specific pathways for the transition to a sustainable agriculture model.

The potential of the 3H practice for facilitating transformative change is well-recognized in the literature (Sharpe et al., 2016). In our research, we found that the primary outcomes from the 3H-CLD workshops (i.e., themes concerning the desired futures, current challenges, and strategies to achieve the desired futures) could hardly be directly usable to support transformative change in the study area since they needed to be further developed through different methods and techniques. From the beginning, we considered that such outcomes needed to be integrated through a cross-scale analysis to support policy coherence in SDG implementation in the study area. The cross-scale analysis supported the idea that all sustainability aspects should be combined and addressed to have a sustainable impact at other scales, areas, and issues (Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021). This is in accordance with similar studies developed in other contexts (e.g., Folhes et al., 2015; Aguiar et al., 2020). With the purpose of our research to provide solutions for supporting transformative change, we framed the cross-scale analysis in a reflexive research approach aiming at working and engaging participants in creating tangible outcomes that may be translatable to the social-ecological systems' reality. This way, once the workshops were finished, we examined the elicited knowledge from participants through a mixed-method approach combining well-established qualitative and quantitative techniques for data analysis. The results were presented and sent iteratively to participants for feedback and refinements. Once an agreement was reached, the results were also considered as input for subsequent workshops that formed

part of the science-action process to co-create an action plan to advance SDG implementation in the region (beyond the scope of this study). This reflexive research approach is increasingly adopted by scholars interested in supporting transformative change for sustainability through the 3H practice (e.g., Aguiar et al., 2020; Collste et al., 2023; Buckton et al., 2024). While we argue that the 3H-CLD has the potential to support transformative change through coherent multi-scale governance needed to achieve global sustainability goals, at present, we are still determining whether our results will serve as a basis to advance toward global sustainability goals in the region. It is widely recognized that multiple institutional, economic, and social factors (e.g., absence of political will, lack of resources and time availability, and scarce organizational capacity) could intervene (Lawrence, 2021). It would be interesting for future research to assess and monitor if/how our research will provide guidance to support real transformative change toward sustainability in the region.

4.4. Limitations of the research

While our study insights provide valuable contributions to show the potential of the 3H-CLD to support policy coherence at multiple governance scales for advancing SDG implementation through dialogue between actors from multiple sectors, we assume that our research may have certain limitations. As with all participatory research approaches, the empirical results collected through the workshops depend on knowledge and perspectives stemming from the relative sample size of workshop participants. Although an effort was made to have a diverse sample of the population during the workshops, they may not fully capture the whole diversity of perspectives that exist across the larger population in the study area. Thereby, results (i.e., the desired futures and concerns and the strategies) may be subjected to potential sampling bias that lies in the systematic exclusion or over-representation of certain groups within the population. However, the high number of themes that emerged across the four workshops indicates a wide diversity of viewpoints. In this regard, we want to highlight that we invited a balanced representation of actors from the different groups to participate in each workshop, but not all responded. Personal communications revealed that multiple factors might be influenced, for example, the voluntary nature of the workshops, time constraints, and the fatigue of being involved in numerous participative processes in the region. Nevertheless, it is important to note that our research did not aim to collect empirical data to make inferences about the whole population; instead, we aimed to explore potential methodological contributions of the 3H-CLD approach to support policy coherence at multiple governance scales for SDG implementation through dialogue between actors from multiple sectors for which the participants' sample provided a wide range of valuable insights to its comprehensive analysis. We think it would be interesting if future research focused on applying the 3H-CLD with a representative sample of individuals without bias to make inferences about the entire population in the study area.

While the replicability of this study may be considered an inherent limitation due to the insights derived from the particular case of the Spanish drylands region, our research provides a helpful contextual guide to develop future 3H-CLD processes to support policy coherence from a multi-scale governance perspective for advancing SDG implementation.

5. Conclusions

This study provides evidence that the 3H-CLD can be a powerful method for supporting policy coherence from a multi-scale governance perspective by engaging actors from various sectors for SDG implementation since it helps to identify 1) future and current themes that can be used as a baseline to harmonize policy priorities by recognizing commonalities and different contextual realities, and 2) associations between strategies that can be used as a starting point to coordinate

actions in alignment with the 2030 Agenda. We highlight the potential of the 3H-CLD as a tool to support transformative change through coherent multi-scale governance needed to achieve global sustainability goals. The policy community can use it to collaboratively plan policies and strategic actions for the region's sustainable future by involving state and non-state actors to deal with social-ecological changes for future transformation toward sustainability.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

María D. López-Rodríguez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Amanda Jiménez-Aceituno:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Cristina Quintas-Soriano:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Juan Miguel Requena-Mullor:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Enrica Garau:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Daniela Alba-Patiño:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Irene Otamendi-Urroz:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Ana Paula D. Aguiar:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Sofía Cortés-Calderón:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Antonio J. Castro:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2024.102922>.

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